

Cyber Insurance and Security Interdependence: Friends or Foes?

Ganbayar Uuganbayar^{1,2}, Artsiom Yaustiukhin¹, and Fabio Martinelli¹

¹Istituto di Informatica e Telematica, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Pisa, Italy,,
Email: {ganbayar.uuganbayar, artsiom.yaustiukhin, fabio.martinelli}@iit.cnr.it

²Department of Information and Communication Technology, University of Trento, Italy,,
Email: ganbayar.uuganbayar@unitn.it

Abstract—Cyber insurance is a cyber risk treatment option which allows transferring losses to another party for a fee. Although researchers and practitioners see cyber insurance as a desirable practice, the new market faces several practical (e.g., lack of data) and theoretical (effect of security interdependency) challenges. One of the most important questions from the cyber security point of view is whether cyber insurance is an incentive to self-protection investments. Several studies have shown that with cyber insurance available, agents are more willing to buy insurance than investing in self-protection.

In this study, we investigate how security interdependence affects the incentive of agents to invest in self-protection with/without cyber insurance available to them. In particular, we are interested in comparing the investments with and without insurance available for agents when the degree of interdependence changes. In the study, we model a competitive cyber insurance market and assume no information asymmetry.

Index Terms—cyber-insurance, interdependency of security, self-protection

I. INTRODUCTION

Adaption of the best cyber security practices and implementation of various countermeasures still does not guarantee 100% protection from incidents to occur. Moreover, the cost of security is high, which makes implementation of all possible security practices and countermeasures cost-inefficient. In other words, organization always face residual risk which they have to accept [2]. Recently, cyber-insurance appeared on the market that allows transferring residual risks to insureds (demand side that purchases an insurance).

By smoothing the expected losses for insureds, insurance companies collect incident data and use them for a more precise further cyber risk estimation [3]. With these risk estimation, insurance companies specify a premium (a fee for risk transfer) which may serve as an indicator of security strength [1]. Furthermore, cyber-insurance is believed to lead to new and more advanced standards in cyber security [3]. Last but not least, cyber-insurance may incentivise insureds to invest more in self-protection so as to get lower premiums [11], [14]. However, some researchers argue that competitive cyber-insurance is not always an incentive for self-protection without regulatory constraints [5], [6]. In other words, according to the studied behaviour models, insureds are often willing to buy

more insurance instead of mitigating their risks. This has a negative effect on the society as a whole, as cyber security is interdependent, i.e., the protection level of one agent depends on other agents that are protected [1].

The studies, which analyse the behaviour of agents without regulation mechanisms (e.g., [5]), also detect the drop in self-protection investments caused by security interdependence if we compare these investments with an independent case. On the other hand, there is lack of a rigorous analysis of how security interdependency affects the ratio of investments in case of whether cyber-insurance is available or not. In other words, the question we would like to answer in this paper is: *can higher security interdependence make investments in self protection with cyber insurance higher than in case when the insurance option is not available.*

In this study, we analyse the impact of security interdependence on the incentive of agents to invest in self-protection with/without cyber-insurance available to them. In particular, we are interested in comparing the investments as the degree of interdependence increases. We have the primary interest in the situation, in which, without interdependency, investments in self-protection with cyber insurance are lower than if insurance is not available. In the work, we model a competitive insurance market and assume no information asymmetry between an agent and an insurer.

Our main contribution of this paper is a formal analysis of the security interdependence impact on investment in self-protection. This work investigates whether cyber insurance can become more incentivising to invest in self protection with the growth of security interdependence.

The remainder of paper is unfolded as follows. In the next section (Section III) we describe the basic formal model considering two cases: i) cyber-insurance is not available to agents and ii) cyber-insurance is available. Then, this section analyses the impact of interdependence on investments in both cases. We conclude the paper with related work (Section IV) and conclusion (Section V).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the realm of cyber security, interconnectedness of nodes is one of the critical challenges so-called security interdependence (i.e., one's security depends on other's security investment). Therefore, it is crucial to analyse its impact

on security, especially, for the decision-making. Assuming that organization (insured) has no either ex-ante control (risk mitigation) or insurance (risk transferring) initially and is willing to protect their assets against cyber risk. Although there is another option so-called risk avoidance, we are not considering this alternative in our case due its rare usage. The goal of this paper is to analyse the interplay between security investment in self-protection, cyber-insurance, and security interdependence in theoretical way. In this work, we consider the situation when there is high security interdependence as opposed to other works where they are focused on a situation with low security interdependence. The following table reveals the main problem that we are trying to cope with:

	Insurance	No-Insurance
Low Π	x	x
High Π	x	x

,where security interdependence is denoted as Π and security investment in self-protection as x . When the security is independent or has low interdependent, it has been proposed by some researchers that security investment in insurance case is lower than no-insurance case. Moreover, there is a drop in security investment in self-protection as security interdependence increases. However, there is a gap that no complete answer in comparison of security investment in both cases when security interdependence is high. Thus, our main problem to solve in this paper is; *"what is the impact of high security interdependence on security investment in both cases?"*.

III. ANALYSIS

For our analysis, we apply the formalisation similar to the one used by H. Ogut et. al [5], I. Ehrlich and G. S. Becker [6], W. Shim [15]. Here we provide a brief introduction of the main concepts of cyber insurance and refer the interested readers to A. Marotta et. al [2].

Let W be the amount of wealth an agent possesses at some time, and W^0 be the amount in the beginning of the considered period. We would like to analyse how the agent is going to behave (i.e., plan its investments) in the following period. We assume, that knowing the investments in self-protection x and the degree of security interdependence Π , we can find the probability of an event to occur as $pr(x, \Pi)$. This probability depends on both direct probability of attack $\pi(x)$ and aggregated probability of contagion $(1 - \Pi)$, and can be found as:

$$pr(x, \Pi) = 1 - (1 - \pi(x))\Pi. \quad (1)$$

It is natural to assume that the probability of direct attack $\pi(x)$ decreases with increase of security investments ($\pi' < 0$) and the efficacy of investments decreases ($\pi'' > 0$). The aggregated probability of contagion $(1 - \Pi_i)$ per agent i , may be computed with the usual approach (see [2], [5]) if the investments of

all agents in the network x_j and the bilateral probabilities of contagion $q_{i,j}$ are known:

$$1 - \Pi_i = 1 - \prod_{\forall j \neq i} (1 - q_{i,j} * \pi(x_j)). \quad (2)$$

Since, for our work these details are irrelevant, we use only Π and skip the index i so as to avoid theoretical complexities. Moreover, we call Π as a degree of interdependence, since it defines how much the security of the network affects the security level of a considered agent. The value from $[0;1)$ interval defines an interdependent case with some degree where the situation is obviously independent if $\Pi = 1$.

An agent uses a utility function to compute its satisfaction of possessing a certain wealth $U(W)$ and returns a positive real value. This function is a concave ($U' \geq 0$, $U'' \leq 0$) Von Neumann–Morgenstern utility function, usually applied in insurance. Now, if losses from an incident are equal to L , then if no insurance is available to an agent its expected utility is:

$$E[U(W)] = U_{NN} * (1 - pr(x, \Pi)) + U_{NL} * pr(x, \Pi), \quad \text{where} \quad (3)$$

$$U_{NN} = U(W - x) \text{ if no incident occurs;} \quad (4)$$

$$U_{NL} = U(W - L - x) \text{ if an incident occurs.} \quad (5)$$

In order to find the optimal amount of investments for an agent, we should consider the first order condition (FOC) and find that it is a solution to the following equation:

$$\pi'(x^N)\Pi = \frac{(1 - (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi)U'_{NL} + (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi * U'_{NN}}{(U_{NL} - U_{NN})}. \quad (6)$$

If insurance option is available, the agent may pay a premium P and get indemnity I in case an incident happens. In the competitive cyber insurance market, no insurer may introduce a new contract more attractive for insureds, than the already available ones. In the model, this means that premiums are fair $P = pr(x, \Pi) * I$. In this case, the expected utility is:

$$E[U(W)] = U_{IN} * (1 - pr(x, \Pi)) + U_{IL} * pr(x, \Pi); \quad \text{where} \quad (7)$$

$$U_{IN} = U(W - pr(x, \Pi) * I - x) \text{ no incident occurs;} \quad (8)$$

$$U_{IL} = U(W - L - pr(x, \Pi) * I + I - x) \text{ incident occurs.} \quad (9)$$

Now, we should consider FOC for I as well as for x . As has been provided by H. Ogut et. al [5] and I. Ehrlich and G. S. Becker [6]. The optimal indemnity I^* is equal to loss L as it is investigated as following proof:

$$\frac{\partial E[U(W)]}{\partial I} = \frac{\partial((pr(x, \Pi) * U_{IL}) + U_{IN}(1 - pr(x, \Pi)))}{\partial I} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$(1 - pr(x, \Pi)) * pr(x, \Pi) * (U'_{IL} - U'_{IN}) = 0. \quad (11)$$

Now, we should consider that $pr(x) = 1$ or $pr(x) = 0$ is fictitious. In reality, if such situations exist, there is no need to purchase insurance. In this regard, we can ignore these cases so that we obtain $U'_{IL} = U'_{IN}$ which leads the following solution for optimal investment:

$$\pi'(x^I)\Pi = -\frac{1}{L}. \quad (12)$$

It is easy to see, that even without solving Equations 6 and 12 we can reason on the values of x^I and x^N : for example, if $\pi'(x^I) > \pi'(x^N)$ investments in case of insurance are higher than in case of no insurance.

From Equations 6 and 12 we see, that in both cases Π affects the amount of optimal investments. We would like to know if there is such Π , which makes $\pi'(x^I) = \pi'(x^N)$. In other words, we would like to know if the following equation holds:

$$\frac{(1 - (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi)U'_{NL} + (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi * U'_{NN}}{(U_{NL} - U_{NN})} = -\frac{1}{L}. \quad (13)$$

We should remind, that x^N depends on Π as Equation 6 states, as well as U_{NN} and U_{NL} depend on x^N , according to Equations 4 and 5. In order to simplify our investigation, the first step is to identify the security interdependence (Π) based on Equation 6 as following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi'(x^N)(U_{NL} - U_{NN})\Pi = \\ & = U'_{NL} - (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi * U'_{NL} + (1 - \pi(x^N))\Pi * U'_{NN} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Above-mentioned transformation leads us to following result:

$$\Pi(\pi(x^N)(U_{NL} - U_{NN}) + (1 - \pi(x^N))(U'_{NL} - U'_{NN})) = U'_{NL} \quad (15)$$

Based on mathematical transformation for defining Π , we are now able to investigate a function fn which is defined by following system¹:

$$\begin{cases} \Pi = \frac{U'_{NL}}{\pi'(x)(U_{NL} - U_{NN}) + (1 - \pi(x))(U'_{NL} - U'_{NN})}; \\ fn = \frac{(1 - (1 - \pi(x))\Pi)U'_{NL} + (1 - \pi(x))\Pi * U'_{NN}}{U_{NL} - U_{NN}}. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Consider two border cases: no interdependence $\Pi = 1$ (with $x^{N_1} = 0$) and some value $1 \geq \bar{\Pi} \geq 0$ which forces the agent to invest 0 into self-protection (i.e., $x^{N_2} = 0$). The most interesting situation is when investments with insurance are lower than without insurance with $\Pi = 1$:

$$\pi'(x^{N_1}) = \frac{\pi(x^{N_1})U'_{NL}(x^{N_1}) + (1 - \pi(x^{N_1}))U'_{NN}(x^{N_1})}{(U_{NL}(x^{N_1}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_1}))} > -\frac{1}{L}. \quad (17)$$

Now, consider another extreme case and prove that there is always a $1 \geq \bar{\Pi} \geq 0$ which force agents to invest $N_2 = 0$ in self-protection. We start with the first equation of equation system 16:

$$\bar{\Pi} = \frac{U'_{NL}(x^{N_2})}{B}; \quad (18)$$

¹Unfortunately, it is impossible to write just one equation as $fn(\Pi)$, since the first equation in the system cannot be shown in an explicit form $x(\Pi)$.

where

$$B = \pi'(x^{N_2})(U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2})) + (1 - \pi(x^{N_2}))(U'_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U'_{NN}(x^{N_2})). \quad (19)$$

Since $x^{N_2} = 0$ and $x^{N_1} \geq 0$, we have that:

$$x^{N_2} \leq x^{N_1} \quad (20)$$

$$\pi(x^{N_2}) \geq \pi(x^{N_1}) \quad (21)$$

$$1 - \pi(x^{N_2}) \leq 1 - \pi(x^{N_1}) \quad (22)$$

$$\pi'(x^{N_2}) \leq \pi'(x^{N_1}) \quad (23)$$

$$U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) \leq U_{NL}(x^{N_1}) \quad (24)$$

$$U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2}) \leq U_{NL}(x^{N_1}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_1}) \quad (25)$$

$$U'_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U'_{NN}(x^{N_2}) \leq U'_{NL}(x^{N_1}) - U'_{NN}(x^{N_1}). \quad (26)$$

Now, baring in mind that $\pi'(x) < 0$ and the condition 23, we say that:

$$\begin{aligned} B & < \pi'(x^{N_1})(U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2})) + \\ & (1 - \pi(x^{N_2}))(U'_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U'_{NN}(x^{N_2})) = \\ & U'_{NL} \times \frac{U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2})}{(U_{NL}(x^{N_1}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_1}))} - \\ & (1 - \pi(x^{N_1}))(U'_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U'_{NN}(x^{N_2})) \times \frac{U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2})}{(U_{NL}(x^{N_1}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_1}))} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Now, consider $\Pi = 0$ case. We see, that:

$$\frac{U'_{NL}(x^{N_2})}{(U_{NL}(x^{N_2}) - U_{NN}(x^{N_2}))} < -\frac{1}{L}, \quad (29)$$

since for a concave function $U'_{NL} * L > U_{NN} - U_{NL}$. Since function $fn(\Pi)$ is continuous, then according to the Intermediate Value Theorem, there is such $1 > \bar{\Pi} > 0$ which makes $fn(\bar{\Pi}) = -\frac{1}{L}$ and Equation 13 holds for this $\bar{\Pi}$.

IV. RELATED WORK

Recently, cyber-insurance gained much attention of practitioners and researchers. The young market faces a number of issues that slow down its maturation [2], [12]. One of these issues relates to interdependency of cyber security and its effect on both cyber-insurance and investments in self-protection [4], [5], [8], [13]. In particular, some researchers have found that if cyber insurance is available investments in self-protection drop [4], [5], [9]. In contrast, M. Lelarge and J. Bolot [8] have shown that cyber security is a mechanism to incentivise agents to invest in self-protection. Here we would like to underline that that the investment model of M. Lelarge and J. Bolot [8] is binary: either low or high level of protection is possible; while H. Ogut et. al, [5] and Shetty and Schwartz et. al, [4], [9] use the continuous investment model, i.e., any additional investment improves the security level. In our paper we have used the continuous investment model and have shown that whether cyber-insurance is an inventive or not may depend on the degree of security interdependence.

A number of authors considered the problem of reducing self-protection level if cyber insurance is available [4], [8], [13], [16] and whether the socially optimum level of investments can be reached [9] [4]. The best solution found so far is a “fines and rebates” mechanism that penalises the agents with low security and grants bonuses to the agents with high security in addition to premium discrimination [7], [8], [13]. In order to use this mechanism, an insurer must have complete information about insureds investments, i.e., there should be no information asymmetry. Furthermore, the work of P. Naghizadeh and M. Liu [10] could be seen as a variation of this mechanism. Their approach requires insurers to collect the proposals for the desired investment level and premiums from all agents. These proposals are adopted to define the pricing strategy for the insurer which leads to the socially optimal investment level if participation is mandatory. In contrast to all these works, we do not consider additional regulation mechanisms in the model, but only analyse the expected behaviour of agents (their investment strategy) in the network with different degree of security interdependence.

V. CONCLUSION

In the paper we have mathematically analysed how the degree of interdependency affects cyber security self-investments with and without cyber insurance available to the considered agent. We have found that if initially, i.e., without interdependence, investments in self-protection are higher in case of no insurance available, then with a certain degree of interdependence, cyber insurance will incentivise to invest in self protection equally to (and even more comparing with) the case if no insurance is available. In other words, we may conclude that interdependent cyber security world has a greater chance to benefit from applying cyber insurance, not only because of its attractiveness for agents but also because of the increase in the self-protection.

The analysis we have presented is far from being complete. For example, in the paper we did not consider the case, when cyber insurance is initially (independent case) incentivise to invest in self protection more than if no insurance available. We have not provided a complete answer on when the ratio of self-protection investments in two cases rises or drops with the change of the degree of interdependence. We also acknowledge that in our model only the considered agent is allowed to purchase insurance and the rest of the network is not. These questions we would like to investigate in our future work. Nevertheless, we see that even the initial analysis already leads to an interesting result.

REFERENCES

[1] A.Laszka, M.Felegyhazi, L. Buttyan: A survey of interdependent security games. *ACM Computing Surveys* 47(23), 2015.
 [2] A.Marotta, F.Martinelli, S.Nanni, A.Orlando, A.Yautsiukhin: Cyber-insurance survey. *Computer Science Review* 24, 35–61 (May 2017)
 [3] ENISA. (2014, Dec) Incentives and barriers of the cyber insurance market in europe. [ONLINE]. Available: goo.gl/BtNyj4

[4] G.A.Schwartz, S.S.Sastry: Cyber-insurance framework for large scale interdependent networks. In: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on High Confidence Networked Systems, HiCoNS '14.*, pp. 145–154. ACM, 2014.
 [5] H.Ogut, N.Menon, S.Raghunathan: Cyber insurance and it security investment: Impact of interdependent risk. In: *Proceedings of the 4th Workshop on the Economics of Information Security*, 2005.
 [6] I.Ehrlich, G.S.Becker: *Market Insurance, Self-Insurance, and Self-Protection Foundations of Insurance Economics.*, chap. Economics and Finance, pp. 164–189. Springer Netherlands, 1992.
 [7] M.Lelarge, J.Bolot: Economic incentives to increase security in the internet: The case for insurance. In: *Proceedings of the 28th IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications.*, pp. 1494–1502, April 2009.
 [8] M.Lelarge, J.Bolot: Network externalities and the deployment of security features and protocols in the internet. In: *Proceedings of the 2008 International conference on Measurement and modeling of computer systems.* vol. 36, pp. 37–48 (June 2008)
 [9] N.Shetty, G.Schwartz, J.Walrand: Can competitive insurers improve network security? In: A.Acquisti, S.Smith, A.R.Sadeghi (eds.) *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Trust and Trustworthy Computing.*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 6101, pp. 308–322. Springer (2010)
 [10] P.Naghizadeh, M.Liu: Voluntary participation in cyber-insurance markets. In: *Proceedings of the 2014 Annual Workshop on Economics in Information Security*, 2014.
 [11] R.Anderson, R.Böhme, R.Claytin, T.Moore.(2016, Jan) Security economics and the internal market.[ONLINE]. Available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/archive>.
 [12] R.Böhme, G.Schwartz: Modeling cyber-insurance : Towards a unifying framework. In: *Proceedings of the 9th Workshop on the Economics in Information Security*, 2010.
 [13] R.Pal, L.Golubchik, K.Psounis, P.Hui: Will cyber-insurance improve network security? a market analysis. In: *Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE Conference on Computer Communications.* pp. 235–243. IEEE (2014)
 [14] R.P.Majuca, W.Yurcik, J.P.Kesan.: The evolution of cyberinsurance. *The Computing Research Repository* pp. 1–16, 2006.
 [15] W.Shim: An analysis of information security management strategies in the presence of interdependent security risk. *Asia Pacific Journal of Information Systems* 22(1), 79–101, March 2012.
 [16] Z.Yang, Lui, J.C.: Security adoption and influence of cyber-insurance markets in heterogeneous networks. *Performance Evaluation* 74, 1–17 (April 2014)

LIST OF FIGURES

1 main problem. 6

Fig. 1. main problem.